

REGRET AND COUNTERFACTUAL THINKING IN MATT HAIG'S *THE MIDNIGHT LIBRARY: A FUNCTIONAL PSYCHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS*

¹Muhammad Hamza, ²Muhammad Aqeel Abbas, ³Muhammad Diljan

¹BS English, University of Malakand, Pakistan.

²BS English, University of Malakand, Pakistan.

³BS English, University of Malakand, Pakistan.

¹hamzamkd2003@gmail.com, ²muhammadaqeelabbas31@gmail.com,

³mdiljan2015@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Abstract

This study examines the effects of regret and counterfactual thinking on decision-making in Matt Haig's novel *The Midnight Library* (2020). Applying Functional Counterfactual Thinking Theory through qualitative analysis and close reading, the research investigates how regret and imagined alternatives shape the protagonist Nora Seed's critical life choices. Findings reveal three pivotal decisions influenced by distinct psychological mechanisms. First, Nora's decision to commit suicide stems from overwhelming, unmanaged regret and persistent upward counterfactual thinking, demonstrating the dysfunctional nature of unregulated emotional processes. Second, her choices to explore alternative lives in the metaphysical library are driven by inaction regret and upward counterfactual thinking as she seeks idealised versions of existence. Third, her ultimate decision to embrace her original life emerges through downward counterfactual thinking, which provides emotional relief by imagining worse outcomes. The study concludes that uncontrolled regret and excessive upward counterfactual thinking lead to dysfunction, while downward counterfactual thinking facilitates emotional regulation and acceptance, achieving the affective function of counterfactual processes.

Introduction

Over the last few years, psychological science has started looking into the nature of profound impacts of regret and counterfactuals on the mental process of decision-making. Regret, as an emotion, is an experience felt universally when a person concludes that an alternative decision would have resulted in a more satisfying outcome (Landman, 1987; Zeelenberg & Pieters, 2007). Counterfactual thinking, that is, the consideration of a past scenario and imagining alternative outcomes, is an integral part of the process of regret. It aids people in formulating “what if” questions, which may serve to be either positive or negative (and sometimes both) for the individual’s mental equilibrium (Byrne, 2005; Roese, 1997). These interrelated aspects of thinking have a significant bearing on the decision-making process, particularly given how life is organised in its intricate and sophisticated manner, as Kahneman (2011) points out, there is a need to be able to learn from a given situation or experience to act accordingly.

The phenomena of regret and counterfactual thinking interface through two distinct mechanisms. Upward counterfactual thinking concerns an individual’s ability to conjure alternative prospects that are better than what happened. This imaginal activity, while often generating regret, serves a motivational pre-emptive function that enables an individual to learn from previous failures (Roese & Epstude, 2008). In contrast, downward counterfactual thinking is the ability to imagine worse possibilities than what happened, which, as a result, provides a sense of relief and aids people in managing their emotions (Epstude & Roese, 2008). Roese and Epstude (2008), in their Functional Counterfactual Thinking Theory, describe these simulated realities as counterproductive. Instead, these are counterfactual thoughts that fulfil a guiding function for the future both in terms of actions as well as in terms of emotions. Under the veil of regret, one’s decision is no longer being made in isolation. It is the process of evaluating the specific outcomes of an option alongside the outcomes of the selected option (Bell, 1982; Loomes & Sugden, 1982). Such thought processes are a blueprint for all future actions that a decision-maker will undertake.

Literature, as a domain of the artful exercise of the human mind, provides a translation of more ‘scientific’ mental structures, such as human drives, determinants, and behaviours. Such intricate narratives as those found in Matt Haig’s contemporary novel, *The Midnight Library* (2020), present a perfect case study on the intricate relationship between regret and counterfactual thinking. The book’s main character, Nora Seed, epitomises the plight of a regretful individual. This thirty-six-year-old appears to have lost everything, including her job, relationships, and a sense of purpose. Convinced that her life is a succession of poor decisions, Nora’s solution is to end her life. Once her decision is made, rather than dying, she finds herself in a bizarre library in a kind of limbo, life and death, where each tome before her is a life she could have lived had she made different choices.

He takes the psychological components that comprise counterfactual thinking and turns them into story-like experiences. *The Midnight Library* allows Nora to live the lives she fantasises about where she had been married to her ex-fiancé, gone to the Olympics to pursue her swimming career, been in a band with her brother, or visited Australia with her best friend (Haig, 2020). Each choice embodies inaction regret (possible regrets) or regret (decisions made that resulted in failures). As Roese and Summerville (2005) noted, inactions tend to be the most regretted over the longest period. During these parallel lives that Nora experiences, she comes to terms with the fact that each of them has its own set of dissatisfactions and even failures. This leads her to a crucial reflection on her current reality, values, and a certain acceptance of her original life.

Although the implications of regret, both philosophical and psychological, are quite common, there is a lack of studies that explore these concepts in relation to decision-making processes in a literary context. There is a thin line between psychology and literature, as documented by Kahneman & Miller (1986) and Zeelenberg et al. (2000); however, much remains to be discovered within the domain of literary studies. This is the purpose of the current study: the examination of *The Midnight Library* using Functional Counterfactual Thinking Theory. *The Midnight Library* by Matt Haig, published in 2020, serves as the primary text. The primary question that this line of thought seeks to answer is as follows: What is the role of regret and counterfactual thinking in Nora's decision-making processes?

In this regard, the study points out three choices that are decisive and shaped by both counterfactual thinking and intense regret. The decision to die by suicide, coupled with regret as well as counterfactual thinking, is the apex of rationality and persistence of a counterfactual thought process that is dysfunctional and counterproductive; her later choices to take a lifeboat and explore other lives set out in the library as a result of action regret, coupled with counterfactual thinking in the upward direction, as the ideal is an idealised self; and finally, the changed lifeworld, to own and center which an altered lifeworld the decision hinges emotionally and in counterfactual thinking is the lifeworld of affection (Markman et al., 2009). Analysing these types of decisions and describing them in a psychological context enables understanding of how regret and counterfactual reasoning serve not only as emotional reactions but also as critical elements in decision-making and individual development.

Literature Review

Theoretical Foundations of Counterfactual Thinking

Epstude and Roese (2008) propose a functional theory of counterfactual thinking, which states that counterfactuals are not just imagined alternatives but serve different psychological functions. They explain two types of counterfactual thinking: upward counterfactual thinking, where a person imagines a better outcome, and downward counterfactual thinking, where a worse outcome is imagined. Upward counterfactual thinking evokes regret but serves as a preparative function, preparing a person for the

future by learning from past mistakes. Downward counterfactual thinking leads to relief by performing the affective function of regulating emotion. Content-specific pathways directly affect a person's future behaviours, while content-neutral pathways influence a person's general mindset, emotion, and motivation.

Kahneman and Miller (1986), in their Norm Theory, argue that people evaluate outcomes by comparing them with what they see as usual or expected outcomes. When a person imagines alternatives more easily, they experience greater regret about the mutability of events. Regret occurs mostly when adverse outcomes come from a decision that deviates from routine behavior or normal actions. Violations of norms generate counterfactual thinking. People in the short-term regret actions more than inactions, especially when the performed actions do not meet expected behavior. Events that are close in time and place evoke stronger counterfactual thinking.

Byrne (2005) argues that when people imagine alternatives (counterfactual thinking), they construct alternatives to actual outcomes based on their logical understanding. People want to erase unexpected and abnormal actions instead of routine ones. Counterfactual thinking starts as a logical process but leads to moral judgments, regret, and self-blaming. People try to change one part of reality at a time while engaging in counterfactual thinking, focusing on the most controllable or causal aspect of the situation. Counterfactual thinking supports learning and moral reasoning.

Nature and Functions of Regret

Landman (1987) defines regret as a complex emotional feeling that includes elements of cognition, emotion, and motivation. Regret derives from counterfactual thinking, imaginings of superior outcomes. She elucidates different types of regret: action regret is the feeling of remorse from acts that one has made. In contrast, inaction is the feeling of remorse from an opportunity missed or an act that one has not undertaken. She further examines moral regret, which is concerned with ethics, and existential regret, which is concerned with the self. She asserts that, contrary to claims that regret is solely negative and irrational, it also has an adaptive value. Individuals experience regret because they regard themselves as accountable for the decision that is made. Regret arises not only from individualistic factors but also due to societal, cultural, and normative pressures to act responsibly. Her research suggests that regret serves both cognitive and preparative functions. Regret helps people manage mistakes and self-regulate for future actions. Ultimately, inaction is desired more strongly than action.

Bourgeois-Gironde (2010) suggests that the feeling of regret serves a purpose in decision-making processes. For him, regret is not irrational, but a constructive element that shapes a decision. In theory, ignoring regret in a decision-making process is a constraint that disregards a characteristic of human nature: the tendency to consider regret. Regret, in this case, is stronger than all other emotions. Regret is not only an experienced feeling but also something expected, making it both backward and forward

looking. Regret and future decision-making, as studied in neuroscientific research, are connected through regret-related neural activations.

Zeelenberg et al. (2000) differentiate regret from disappointment. Regret is mainly caused when people believe that their actions lead to worse outcomes; it is more self-focused. Disappointment, on the other hand, does not involve self-blaming and personal responsibility. Regret affects choices before and after a decision; anticipated regret influences a person's decision before they make a choice, while experienced regret shapes future behaviour and self-evaluation. People often leave a potential choice to avoid the anticipated regret, even if the rewards are high. Their experiment shows that people, when not taking actions, regret it more than failed ones. People often regret future behaviour; in some cases, they avoid choices with more benefits to avoid self-blaming.

Regret Regulation and Decision-Making

Pieters et al. (2007), in their Theory of Regret Regulation, propose that regret is not only experienced but can also be regulated by acquiring behaviours that minimise or avoid regret. There are five stages of the regret regulation process: anticipated regret, finding the level of regret before making the decision; preventing regret by choosing a safer option; experiencing regret; regulating regret emotionally and cognitively; and learning from regret. Decisions are influenced mainly by anticipated regret rather than experienced ones. Responsibility determines the intensity of regret and control a person feels for the negative outcome. People minimise regret by delaying decisions, selecting safer options, or completely avoiding situations where there is a chance of regret. Regret is only functional when the emotion is managed effectively.

Summerville and Roese (2009) conducted a study on what people regret most and why. They argue that regret is a universal emotion that arises when people evaluate their lives. They examine which aspect of life has the strongest feeling of regret and why some regrets are more lasting than others. The opportunity principle, a theoretical contribution, suggests that people regret things more intensely when the opportunity for change is still available; high opportunity leads to stronger regret. Findings reveal that the most regretted aspects of life are education, careers, romance, parenting, self-improvement, leisure, finance, family, health, and friendship. The study supports that people regret mostly things they have not done; inactions have more lasting regret than actions.

Beike et al. (2009) argue that the intensity of regret increases when people think they have lost the opportunity permanently and the outcomes are irreversible. Regret is less when there is a chance for the opportunity to come again. When the decision is self-relevant and carries personal importance, it intensifies regret. Empirical data show that regret from lost opportunities was rated stronger than regret from ongoing opportunities. Perception also matters, not just the loss of the opportunity if a person perceives the opportunity to be closed and irreversible.

Emotions and Decision-Making Processes

Lerner et al. (2015) explain that regret is not incidental but arises from a decision experience and guides future choices. The positive and negative aspects of an emotion are not sufficient to trigger regret or inform the decision-making process. It is responsible for appraising different emotions that have the same consequence, such as anger, which can result in positive and risky outcomes, whereas fear leads to conservative outcomes. Such evaluative pathways, which determine decision outcomes, have been demonstrated in neuroscience. Matarazzo et al. (2021) refuted the idea that personal responsibility and decision-making lead to regret, arguing that even forced decisions can cause regret. Regret is felt even when outcomes are more favourable, as it depends on the individual's emotions.

The literature shows that regret and counterfactual thinking are advanced psychological concepts with important implications for the decision-making process in both constructive and destructive routes, thus providing ample theoretical support for their study.

Methodology

This research adopts a qualitative approach to examine how regret and counterfactual thinking influence decision-making in *The Midnight Library* (2020), written by Matt Haig. As Kothari (2004) suggests, qualitative research plays a vital role in behavioural sciences by aiming to reveal and deepen understanding of complex psychological issues. Instead of using a quantitative approach that examines relationships through numbers, this qualitative study employs comprehensive textual analysis. It considers and collects interpretive data to form a richly detailed understanding of the protagonist's emotional and rational components of thinking as expressed in the narrative.

Matt Haig's *The Midnight Library* (2020) forms the basis of the primary data for this study. Alongside this primary text, the research incorporates secondary data in the form of scholarly publications, psychological textbooks, and theoretical discourse on the topics of counterfactual thinking, regret and decision-making. The secondary literature serves to provide the theoretical underpinning that validates the interpretation of the primary text and lays the groundwork for scholarly discourse regarding the analysis. Theoretical perspectives that shape and inform this study derive from the work of Roese and Epstude (2008) and their Functional Counterfactual Thinking Theory, which asserts that counterfactual thinking serves a motivational and regulatory function within human behaviour.

The data was collected and analysed through close reading of the text, a method that requires careful examination to identify patterns, themes, and core texts relevant to the study. To grasp all data that pertains to the themes of regret, counterfactual thinking and decision-making, multiple reading sessions of the text were undertaken. The focus was on moments when the protagonist, Nora Seed, is said to regret, think counterfactually, and make decisions.

Key passages were identified, highlighted and analysed for their psychological implications and their placement within the theoretical framework. Supplementary to these strategies, the technique of character analysis was used, focusing on Nora Seed's psychological growth, personality, and the decisions made while on the thrilling journey. This technique offers a vital insight into the character's mental state, her motivations, and the flexibility of her thinking and behaviour at specific points in the narrative. This research examines upward and downward counterfactual thinking through which a respondent interacts.

The data analysis procedure involved reading the text data related to functional counterfactual thinking theory and identifying instances of upward counterfactual thinking, downward counterfactual thinking, and various forms of regret, including action, inaction, and experienced regret. Using this approach provides a deeper understanding of the psychology at play in the text and the psychological constructs that shape the character's actions, decisions, and development.

Data Analysis

The analysis of Matt Haig's *The Midnight Library* reveals how regret and counterfactual thinking profoundly influence the protagonist Nora Seed's decision-making processes. Through close examination of the text, three critical decisions emerge as pivotal moments shaped by different manifestations of regret and counterfactual thinking: the decision to die, the decision to choose alternative lives, and the decision to live. Each decision demonstrates distinct psychological mechanisms operating within the framework of Functional Counterfactual Thinking Theory.

The Decision to Die: Dysfunctional Regret and Upward Counterfactual Thinking

Nora's initial decision to commit suicide represents the most extreme consequence of unmanaged regret and persistent upward counterfactual thinking. At the beginning of the novel, Nora is consumed by overwhelming regret about her life choices. She views her existence as a series of failures, stating: "Every move had been a mistake, every decision a disaster, every day a retreat from who she'd imagined she'd be" (Haig, 2020, p.20). This passage reveals the intensity of her self-blame and the cumulative effect of perceived wrong choices.

The depth of Nora's despair is further articulated when she reflects: "I had all the chances to make something of my life, and I blew every one of them. Through my own carelessness and misfortune, the world has retreated from me, and so now it makes perfect sense that I should retreat from the world" (Haig, 2020, p.21). This statement demonstrates multiple types of regret operating simultaneously: inaction regret over missed opportunities and existential regret related to her sense of identity and life purpose. Nora engages in upward counterfactual thinking, constantly imagining better versions of her life that could have existed if she had made different choices.

The decision to end her life represents the maladaptive function of counterfactual thinking. Rather than serving the preparative function identified by Roese and Epstude (2008), where regret motivates positive behavioural change, Nora's uncontrolled regret leads to complete dysfunction. She fails to manage her emotions effectively, and her persistent focus on imagined better alternatives without taking practical steps toward change intensifies her emotional distress. As she stares at a magazine cover depicting a black hole, she realises, "that is what she was. A black hole. A dying star. Collapsing in on itself" (Haig, 2020, p.12). This metaphor captures how unregulated regret and counterfactual thinking can consume a person entirely, leading not just to emotional withdrawal but to the ultimate physical withdrawal, death.

This first decision demonstrates that while counterfactual thinking can be functional, it becomes destructive when individuals become trapped in continuous loops of upward comparison without emotional regulation or behavioural adaptation. Nora's decision to die emerges from this dysfunctional state, showing how regret, when improperly managed, can overwhelm rational decision-making and lead to tragic outcomes.

The Decision to Choose Alternative Lives: Inaction, Regret and Upward Counterfactual Thinking

Nora's experience in the Midnight Library reveals the potential impact of different choices through the different avatars she has the option to live. As Mrs Elm puts it... "Above" and "below" are conventions of life. "In" and "out" are even more so. . . . There is a library. There is a library in which the shelves are infinite. Each book is a chance to live a different life. We live in a world of possibilities. And there are limitless possibilities. What happens If I say we can unmake, I say? What do you change?" (Haig, 2020, p.27). This allows the readers to think of different scenarios and helps the user live in the different realities they try to imagine each day.

Nora's life choices stem from counterfactual reasoning and regrets at any level. Her first choice reflects regret for inaction as it relates to her untangled relationship with Dan. She recalls "chatting late at night with Dan about his dream of owning a quaint little pub in the country. His enthusiasm had been infectious, and it became her dream too" (Haig, 2020, p. 37). She wishes her life did not involve separation from Dan and hopes to lead a life where both are together and can pursue their dreams. This decision shows how regret for inaction influenced the choice of life she ended up with. She focuses on counterfactual thinking, approximating life with Dan, and concludes that it is better than her actual life. Nora comes to know the realities of living the life she fabricates. Dan's voice "didn't sound like she remembered. It sounded emptier. "A bit colder. Maybe it was tiredness. Maybe it was stressful. Maybe it was beer. Maybe it was marriage." (Haig, 2020, p. 48) This realisation of living with choices made becomes the first blow to her expectation of things to be better. This expectation creates dissonance between the imagined and real choices, altering the outcome.

Nora's choice to consider the life of an Olympic swimmer furthers the idea that regret dictates her decisions. She asks: "I want to know the life where I did what my father wanted. The life where I trained as hard as I possibly could... The life where I got obsessed with the music and writing the novels that were never finished... The life where I never stopped" (Haig, 2020, p.77). This decision reveals existential regret for not achieving what her father wanted, as well as regret for inaction in pursuing swimming. The upward counterfactual thinking in this scenario builds a reality where hard work, determination, and validation equals success. She envisions herself fixing the wrongs of the past. She decides to focus on swimming as her primary activity instead of the others, believing this would make her a better person.

Nora's other decisions, such as living with her brother and friends in the band, have also been associated with her regret of not being in the music scene. "She pictured her brother having fun on stage with her and Ravi and Ella. So now she did know which book to ask for" (Haig, 2020, p.139). Every new life she chooses to pursue in her counterfactual alternatives is an attempt to settle the regret and reclaim the better outcomes she has thought of from her upward counterfactual thinking.

Nora's next pivotal decision would be to pursue a life with Ash, her next-door neighbour. Following her unsatisfactory interaction with Dan, she entertains yet another counterfactual, "Years ago, when I was with Dan. I said no, well, because I was with Dan. But what if I hadn't been? Aye, I would love to have a coffee sometime, Ash" (Haig, 2020, p. 197). The very existence of these decisions indicates that every unsatisfactory alternate life scenario gives rise to fresh counterfactual imaginings, forming a "what if" web that endlessly modifies her selection.

Such choices reflect counterfactual thinking's corrective function, where Nora attempts to amend the mistakes she has made in the past by dwelling on these imagined substitutes. However, the pattern also shows that upward counterfactual thinking is skewed, as it is more readily anchored in wishful thinking than plausible substitutes. In the library, Nora's decisions have less to do with genuine finding and more with diminishing the remorse of her counterfactual life, where she is in search of a fantastical life that perhaps does not exist.

The Decision to Live: Downward Counterfactual Thinking and Emotional Relief

Nora experiences a decision-making transformation when she engages in downward counterfactual thinking, considering worse possibilities instead of better ones. This cognitive shift serves the affective function of relief and acceptance as outlined in the Functional Counterfactual Thinking Theory.

An example of the aforementioned downward counterfactual thinking and its consequences occurs in the chapter where Nora learns about the multiple lives of her cat Voltaire. Mrs. Elm describes, "There is a difference, Nora, between dying in a road and being hit by a car. In your root life, Voltaire lived longer than almost any other life except the one you have just encountered... While he had a

tough few years, the year you had him was the best of his life. Voltaire has had much worse lives” (Haig, 2020, p.59). This moment of realisation helps Nora understand that losing her cat was, in fact, a net positive when weighed against the other possible outcomes. This downward shift in comparison provides emotional relief and begins to change her perspective.

The reinforcement of this thinking is found in Mrs. Elm’s instruction: “Click. Moreover, even if you were a pawn—and maybe we all are. Then you should remember that a pawn is the most magical piece of all. It might look small and ordinary but it isn’t. Because a pawn is a queen-in-waiting. All you need to do is find a way to keep moving forward” (Haig, 2020, p.168). This type of thinking is a clear leap from the what-ifs of downward counterfactual thinking to the what-ifs of upward counterfactual thinking.

A critical realisation comes upon Nora after having gone through several alternative lives: “It is easy to mourn the lives we aren’t living. It’s easy to wish we had other talents and to say yes to different offers... It is easy to regret, and regret, and regret, ad infinitum, until there is no more time... But the lives we are not living will not be the real problem. It is the regret. The regret that shrivels and withers, and makes us feel the worst enemy to ourselves and to others” (Haig, 2020, p.248). She does not blame herself for making wrong choices, but rather for not attending to the consequences of regretting possible choices. She realises that a persistent, upward counterfactual cycle of thinking will be self-destructive.

Nora’s final realisation includes downward counterfactual thinking when she states, “And that actually the life she had been living had its own logic to it. Her brother was alive. Izzy was alive. Moreover, she helped a young boy stay out of trouble. What sometimes feels like a trap is actually just a trick of the mind” (Haig, 2020, p.240). Here, the psychological term is a downward counterfactual thinking, as she considers worst-case scenarios (What if Joe is dead? What if Izzy is dead?) and finds relief in the positive attributes of her earlier life that she had ignored.

Nora’s climactic moment occurs when the library begins to dissolve, forcing her to make her final decision. She writes, “Three simple words containing the power and potential of a multiverse... ‘I am alive!’ And with that, the ground shook like fury and every last remnant of the midnight library dissolved into dust” (Haig, 2020, p.242). She makes a claim that underlines her decision to radically change her fundamental life, as she premises her claim on the fact that life includes hardships and regrets. What is the downward counterfactual “What if I was dead” that justifies this decision?

Nora writes down her self-reflections; “We can’t tell if any of those other versions would have been better or worse. Those lives are happening, but you are happening as well, and that is the happening you have to focus on” (Haig, 2020, 248). This quote dismisses possible envisioned lives as wishful thinking and instead opts for a realistic reconciliation with her current status. She understands

that considering better possible outcomes highlights how her original life, with its distinctive set of realities, is invaluable.

Conclusion

This study explored the impact of counterfactual thinking and regret on Nora Seed's decision-making in Matt Haig's *The Midnight Library*, applying the Functional Counterfactual Thinking Theory. The analysis shows that regret and counterfactual thinking profoundly shape the protagonist Nora Seed's three critical life decisions, influencing both the functional and dysfunctional aspects of each process. The results show that unmanaged regret coupled with relentless upward counterfactual thinking results in destructive dysregulation, as depicted in Nora's decision to commit suicide. Chronic regret, coupled with pervasive imaginative thinking, can, in extreme counterfactual cases, generate misery rather than alleviate it. Counterfactual thinking in that case does not fulfil its preparative role, instead extending the emotional suffering. From the counterfactual thinking and inaction regret of Nora, as well as the goal-oriented, upward counterfactual thinking, it can be understood that people often aspire to ideals based on fundamental illusions rather than on improvement. The downward counterfactual, though, really provides the emotional value needed for regulation and acceptance. Embracing the worst, rather than the best, allows emotional relief and recognition of the worth of a life fully lived. In that value shift, the ultimate decision to be is also the decision to be needed. This, indeed, shows the propositive value of counterfactual thinking in the consideration of acceptance.

The research sheds further light on the intersection of psychology and literature, underlining the necessity of learning to manage regret and the regretful narratives we construct. Different studies might address counterfactual thinking and regret in other stories or consider the clinical utility of downward counterfactual thinking for regret sufferers. Ultimately, this analysis indicates that regret, while universal, is shaped by the contours of one's relationship with regret and counterfactual thinking. This relationship, in turn, dictates the extent to which these processes become detrimental or beneficial to one's decision-making and self-development.

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